

**NEW APPEARANCES OF CONFLICT IN THE STORIES
OF THE INDEPENDENCE PERIOD (IN THE EXAMPLE
OF ANDIJAN CREATORS)****Nizomova Guljahon**

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ABSTRACT

This article examines a new artistic interpretation of conflict in the Uzbek short story of the independence period, in particular, in the works of creators belonging to the Andijan literary environment. In the stories created during the years of independence, it is observed that traditional social conflicts are increasingly being replaced by spiritual-moral, psychological and existential conflicts. The contradictions between the hero and society, the individual and the time, the inner "I" and the external environment in the stories of Andijan creators are analyzed and their artistic solutions are revealed. Also, the internalization of the conflict in the stories of the independence period, the transfer of drama to the psychological layer, and its inextricable connection with the national mentality are scientifically illuminated.

Introduction

During the years of independence, Uzbek literature, in particular the short story genre, was significantly updated in terms of content and form. In this process, the human personality, its inner world, spiritual quests, and relationship with society were brought to the center of artistic thought. As a result, the issue of conflict in literary works began to be interpreted in a new way. If in previous periods the conflict was mainly built on the basis of socio-political contradictions, during the period of independence it was manifested more in the form of psychological, spiritual-moral, and internal spiritual conflicts. The Andijan literary environment, as an important component of the Uzbek literature of the period of independence, actively participated in these processes. In the stories of the creators of this region, ordinary human life, its inner experiences, life choices, and relationship with time became the main artistic object. It was this aspect that gave rise to new manifestations of conflict and expanded the psychological possibilities of the short story genre.

Main part

In the period of independence, the issue of artistic conflict began to acquire a new meaning and form in Uzbek literature, especially in the short story genre. This process is clearly manifested in the works of creators belonging to the Andijan literary environment, where it is possible to observe that the conflict has moved beyond the scope of traditional social contradictions and into complex psychological states related to the inner world of the individual. The freedom of society from ideological pressures in the conditions of

independence made it possible to address the human psyche in literature more deeply. As a result, conflict began to be interpreted as spiritual suffering and internal contradictions rather than as an eventful conflict.

In the short stories created by Andijan creators, conflict is often manifested not in the form of the hero's open struggle with society, but through his internal experiences, life choices, and conscientious responsibility. In such works, the hero confronts not an external enemy, but his own fears, hesitations, and views on life. This is one of the important features of the literature of the independence period, which serves to depict the human personality as an independent-thinking subject, feeling moral responsibility. The internalization of the conflict in the stories of the independence period arises, first of all, from the need to deeply reveal the character of the hero. In works created in the Andijan literary environment, heroes are often depicted as individuals living ordinary lives and not having a special position in society. However, their inner world is complex and full of contradictions, and it is these spiritual contradictions that constitute the main conflict of the work. The authors artistically analyze the process of human self-awareness through such conflicts.

One of the important manifestations of conflict in these stories is the contradiction between the individual and the time. The social and spiritual changes that occurred in society during the independence period cause a certain instability in the psyche of the hero. A person caught between old views and the demands of new life experiences an internal conflict. Andijan writers reveal this situation not through sharp dramatism, but through thoughtful, calm, but deep psychological images. As a result, the conflict develops not on the basis of external events, but on the basis of internal experiences. Also, spiritual and moral conflicts occupy a special place in the stories of the independence period. Heroes are often forced to choose between honesty and benefit, conscience and adaptation, tradition and innovation. This choice process, in turn, creates sharp spiritual conflicts in their inner world. In the stories created in the Andijan literary environment, such conflicts are depicted in close connection with the national mentality. Factors such as family, neighborhood, and customs directly influence the hero's decisions, complicating the conflict. Another important aspect of conflict in the stories of the independence period is its lack of an open solution. While in traditional literature, conflict often ends with a specific conclusion or idea, in the stories of the independence period the issue remains open. Andijan writers refrain from strictly assessing the fate of the hero and encourage the reader to draw independent conclusions. This gives the conflict a philosophical content and enhances the aesthetic impact of the work. In addition, in the stories of the independence period, internal conflict is often expressed through language and style. Authors reveal the spiritual conflict using the hero's internal monologues, memories, and symbolic details. The simple but figurative language characteristic of the Andijan literary environment serves to convey the conflict naturally and convincingly, without artificial dramatism. This further expands the psychological possibilities of the story genre. In the stories of the independence period created by Andijan writers, one can see that conflict has risen to a new artistic level. It is now not just a clash of events, but an aesthetic phenomenon that expresses the complex processes of the human psyche. The process of understanding one's identity, coming to terms with time or resisting it serves as the main

source of conflict. This situation indicates the maturity of artistic thinking in the Uzbek stories of the independence period, in particular in the literary environment of Andijan.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that in the stories of the independence period, especially in the works created in the literary environment of Andijan, artistic conflict has been renewed in content and form. Now the conflict is not limited to external events or social contradictions, but has become an important aesthetic tool reflecting internal conflicts in the human psyche. The hero's identity, conscience, life choices and relationship with time are manifested as the main source of conflict. In the stories of Andijan writers, conflict is often expressed not through open dramatic conflicts, but through quiet but deep psychological images. This situation expands the internal possibilities of the story genre and encourages the reader to observe the mental state of the hero. Also, the lack of an open solution to the conflict and the author's abstention from a firm judgment reflect the free artistic thinking inherent in the literature of the independence period.

In general, the process of renewal of conflict poetics is clearly demonstrated in the stories of the independence period created in the literary environment of Andijan. In these works, conflict has become a means of artistic research of a person's spiritual maturity, self-awareness, and relationship with time. This indicates that the Uzbek storytellers of the independence period have reached a mature stage and serve as an important theoretical and practical basis for scientific research in this area.

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